

MODELLING CHARACTERISATION OF A FAST CURING SILICA NANOPARTICLE MODIFIED EPOXY

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ABSTRACT

Fast-curing epoxy polymers allow composite parts to be manufactured in minutes, but the curing reaction is highly exothermic with heat flows up to 20 times higher than conventional epoxies. The low thermal conductivity of the polymer causes the mechanical and kinetic properties of parts to vary through their thickness. In the present work, silica nanoparticles were used to reduce the exotherm, and hence improve the consistency of the manufactured parts. The kinetic properties were measured as a function of part thickness and it was noted that the exothermic heat of reaction can be significantly reduced with the addition of silica nanoparticles, which were well-dispersed in the epoxy. A model was developed to describe the increase in viscosity and degree of cure of the unmodified and the silica-modified epoxies. A heat transfer equation was used to predict the temperature and resulting properties through the thickness of a plate, as well as the effect of the addition of silica nanoparticles. No significant viscosity increase was found with the addition of up to 20 wt% of silica nanoparticles. The predictions were compared to the experimental data, and the agreement was found to be very good.

1 INTRODUCTION

With an increasing demand for composites in the automotive industry, the cycle times for composite parts are driven down from several hours to under 5 minutes. Resin curing is generally a limiting factor for cycle times. Newly developed epoxy systems have cure times of 5 minutes and less. However, the fast cure may lead to a strong exothermic reaction during cross-linking which can lead to a temperature overshoot of the resin compared to the mould temperature and may limit their processability. By combining the heat conduction equation with the cure kinetics, it is possible to predict the actual resin temperature which then can be used to model the kinetic properties and viscosity. These models allow optimised impregnation and cure and could be implemented into a code for modelling the flow in liquid composite moulding processes.

Cure kinetics and rheology have been modelled for slow-curing epoxies [1-3] including the addition of silica nanoparticles [4]. Modelling of these parameters for fast-curing epoxies [5, 6] results in new challenges for accurate measurements to generate these models. The rapid progression of degree of cure and viscosity make it impossible to measure at higher isothermal temperatures, using standard measuring methods, e.g. differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) and plate-plate rheometer. For example Yang et al. [5] found that the total heat of reaction from isothermal DSC measurements decreases at higher temperatures because the heat flow is not measured correctly in the initial stage of curing.

Heat flow in the resin is limited by the low thermal conductivity of the epoxy and therefore it is not possible to transport the heat into a mould quick enough to prevent temperature overshoot of the resin,

even if the mould surface would be increased. A more promising approach is the reduction of the exothermic mass, which can be achieved by adding particles to the resin. The addition of ceramic particles for example will reduce the exothermic heat, as well as reduce cure shrinkage, by reducing the volume of epoxy and increasing the thermal conductivity, as was reported by [7]. For composite manufacturing any such particles must be small such that they are not filtered out during infusion processes, for example silica nanoparticles with a diameter of 20 nm [8]. The addition of silica nanoparticles has previously also been shown to increase stiffness, fracture energy [9-11] and cyclic-fatigue resistance [12].

This suggests that silica nanoparticles may be advantageous when manufacturing components using fast-curing epoxies, so the present work will investigate of the effects of silica nanoparticles on fast-curing resins by studying the curing and rheological behaviour. The rheology and kinetics were modelled, and the variation in the glass transition temperature through the thickness of plates was predicted, and compared with experimental results.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The epoxy resin used was a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy with an epoxy equivalent weight (EEW) of 181.5 g eq⁻¹, “XB 3585” from Huntsman Advanced Materials, Switzerland. The curing agent was a mixture of diethylenetriamine and 4,4'-isopropylidenediphenol, “XB 3458” from Huntsman Advanced Materials, and was used at a stoichiometric ratio of 100:19 by weight of epoxy to hardener.

The silica (SiO₂) nanoparticles were supplied as a masterbatch, “Nanopox F400” from Evonik Hanse, Germany, with 40 wt% of silica nanoparticles predispersed in DGEBA (EEW = 295 g eq⁻¹) with a mean diameter of 20 nm [13]. Formulations with up to 20 wt% of silica nanoparticles (denoted 20N) were used for the mechanical and fracture tests, with some additional measurements with up to 35.8 wt% of silica nanoparticles (35.8N).

The degree of cure, α , and the glass transition temperature, T_g , were measured using a Mettler DSC 1 using 5 mg of resin in “tzero” aluminium pans. Modulated measurements (± 0.30 °C every 15 s) were conducted to determine the glass transition temperature and the residual heat of reaction for the partially-cured resin were performed using a TA Q1000. All the measurements were performed using a nitrogen sample purge flow to reduce oxidation of the resin.

A PAAR Physica MCR 302 plate-plate rheometer or a TA AR 200 EX plate-plate rheometer was used to measure the change in viscosity with a strain of 1 % and an angular frequency of 10 s⁻¹. Disposable aluminium plates of 25 mm diameter were used with a gap of 1 mm between the plates.

Bulk epoxy plates were cast in 8 mm thick aluminium pre-heated moulds.

3 CURE MODELLING

3.1 Introduction

During cure the resin temperature depends on an external heat source, e.g. a mould or an oven and the internal heat generation as a result of the exothermic cross-linking. Depending on the resin used and the thickness of the manufactured parts, the overshoot from resin to mould temperature can be significant. With the studied epoxy for example, a 3 mm plate manufactured in a pre-heated mould at 100 °C resulted in a maximum resin temperature of 176 °C (Figure 1 insert). In order to model the resin temperature, the heat conduction equation with a chemical reaction source term can be used [14],

$$\rho_r H_{tot} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} + \nabla(k\nabla T) = \rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

where ρ_r is the resin density, ρ is the density of the composite, V_r is the volume fraction of resin, H_{tot} is the total heat of reaction, $d\alpha/dt$ is the modelled reaction rate, k is the thermal conductivity and C_p is the specific heat capacity of the epoxy resin.

The reaction rate is proportional to the heat flow and can be directly measured using DSC,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{dH}{H_{tot}} \quad (2)$$

3.2 Measuring the heat flow

The heat flow was measured under isothermal conditions from 60 °C to 100 °C in a 10 °C interval for the unmodified epoxy as shown in Figure 1. Measurements were performed by placing the samples into the pre-heated DSC furnace. Approximately 3 to 4 seconds of data were lost while the DSC chamber closed and began recording the heat flow. This method could be used with the Mettler DSC 1. Despite opening the device, no temperature difference was measured by the DSC.

Figure 1: Shows the measured heat flow for isothermal measurements of the unmodified epoxy.

There are three major findings: i) The heat flow peaks at the beginning of the reaction at a degree of cure of 0.1 for all measurements which indicates that a high amount of heat will be released in the beginning of the cure reaction as observed in Figure 1 insert. ii) The maximum measured heat flow increases exponentially with increasing temperature, and hence the temperature overshoot is expected to be more severe with increasing temperature (Figure 2 left). iii) The measured maximum heat flow during isothermal measurements shows a high magnitude compared to standard curing epoxies, i.e. a factor of 20 higher compared to HexFlow RTM6, a commonly-used epoxy in the aerospace industry (Figure 2 left).

Measurements were repeated with the addition of silica nanoparticles for the range of 70 °C to 100 °C and the same trends were observed but with a reduced heat flow. The addition of these particles reduces the total mass of the epoxy and therefore reduces the heat flow linear to the amount of wt%. The same trend can be observed for measurements under dynamic conditions as shown in Figure 2 right.

Figure 2: (left) Comparison of the maximum heat flow during isothermal conditions, including a reference to RTM6. (right) Dynamic heat flow measurements for the unmodified epoxy, 10 and 20 wt%.

3.3 Determination of total heat of reaction

The total heat of reaction, H_{tot} , is defined as the integral of the measured heat flow, e.g. the area under the curve from Figure 2 right. Dynamic measurement were performed with heating rates, $dT dt^{-1}$, from 10 to 30 °C min^{-1} at 5 °C min^{-1} intervals between room temperature until the material was fully cured. For the unmodified epoxy ΔH_{tot} was measured to be $493.65 \pm 3.16 J g^{-1}$. Measurements were repeated for 10 wt%, 20 wt%, 25 wt% and 35.8 wt% of silica (where 35.8 wt% is the maximum possible amount of silica in the epoxy when mixed with the curing agent). Because of the previously discussed linear reduction of the heat flow with the addition of silica nanoparticles, H_{tot} , decreases linearly as well.

3.4 Kinetic modelling

The linear decrease of both, heat flow and total heat of reaction with the addition of silica nanoparticles leads to identical reaction rates (equation (2)), and hence the kinetic model is independent of the silica content. The kinetic model is based on the approach of Bailleul [15] and the modification by Ruiz et al. [16]. The reaction rate can be modelled as a function of temperature and degree of cure using

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k_1 \cdot e^{\left(-E_1 \left(\frac{T_{ref}-1}{T}\right)\right)} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^m G_i \alpha^i \cdot (\alpha_{max}(T) - \alpha)^n \quad (3)$$

$$\text{with } G(\alpha) = \frac{G_1 \alpha^4 + G_2 \alpha^3 + G_3 \alpha^2 + G_4 \alpha + G_5}{G_6 \alpha^2 + G_7 \alpha} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } \alpha_{max} = \frac{T_c - T_{g0}}{(T_c - T_{g0})(1 - \lambda) + (T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})\lambda} \quad (5)$$

where k_1 is the frequency factor of the cure reaction, E_1 is the activation energy, T_{ref} is a randomly chosen temperature, G_i is a polynomial function, α_{max} is the maximum degree of cure for isothermal curing, n is the power exponent which depends on temperature, T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$ are the glass transition temperature of the uncured and the fully cured material respectively and λ is a fitting parameter

The model parameters are given in Table 1 with the models shown in Figure 3. It shall be noted that no difference in the glass transition temperature values was found with the addition of silica nanoparticles. With R^2 -values between 0.995 and 0.999, the agreement between measured and modelled data is excellent for the dynamic case. Some deviation was found for the isothermal cases. For higher temperatures (80 to 100 °C), the initial curing is modelled well. However, the model overshoots the

measured data as the curing reaction starts before the heat flow is measured by the DSC. This effect increases at higher temperatures, which is reflected in the model. With R^2 -values between 0.981 and 0.997, the fit is still in an acceptable range. The high accuracy of the model is important for the implementation of the reaction rate into the heat conduction model.

Name	Symbol	Value
Polynomial parameter	G_1	-1351
Polynomial parameter	G_2	-2678
Polynomial parameter	G_3	10194
Polynomial parameter	G_4	4338
Polynomial parameter	G_5	-5.208
Polynomial parameter	G_6	587
Polynomial parameter	G_7	4570
Reaction exponent factor slope	n_s	0.018
Reaction exponent factor intercept	n_i	-5.2367
Frequency factor	k_1 (s^{-1})	0.00309
Activation energy	E_1	-22.28
Reference temperature	T_{ref} (K)	350
T_g of the uncured resin	T_{g0} (K)	246.15
T_g of the cured resin	$T_{g\infty}$ (K)	394.4
Parameter for α_{max} model	μ	0.32

Table 1: Fitting parameters for the cure kinetic model.

Figure 3: (left) Cure kinetic model for dynamic measurements and (right) isothermal measurements of the unmodified epoxy.

Further the glass transition temperature, T_g , was modelled as a function of the degree of cure, α , using the DiBenedetto model [17]

$$T_g = T_{g0} + \frac{(T_{g\infty} - T_{g0})\lambda\alpha}{1 - (1-\lambda)\alpha} \quad (6)$$

where T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$ are the glass transition temperature of the uncured and the fully cured material respectively, given in section 3.1 and the fitting parameter, λ equals 0.45. Measurements were obtained using a modulated DSC set-up. The T_g was measured directly from the reversible heat flow, and α was determined from the residual heat of reaction from the irreversible heat flow.

3.5 Modelling the heat transfer

The heat conduction model (equation (1)) was solved in one dimension to account for a thickness-dependent temperature overshoot to give

$$\rho_r H_{tot} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} + k_{xx} \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} = \rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad (7)$$

where ρ_r is the resin density, ρ is the density of the composite, V_r is the volume fraction of resin, H_{tot} is the total heat of reaction, $d\alpha/dt$ is the modelled reaction rate, k_{xx} is the thermal conductivity and C_p is the specific heat capacity of the epoxy resin.

Equation (7) was discretised in Matlab using the finite element method with linear elements according to [14], leading to an equation in the form

$$C\dot{T} + K T - F = 0 \quad (8)$$

where C is the thermal capacity matrix, K is the thermal conductivity matrix and F is the thermal load vector due to chemical reaction of the resin, with

$$C = \int_l \rho C_p N^T N dx \quad (9)$$

$$K = \int_l k_{xx} \dot{T}^T \dot{T} dx \quad (10)$$

$$F = \int_l N^T \rho_r H_{tot} \frac{d\alpha}{dt} dx \quad (11)$$

where N is the shape function.

A finite difference scheme was used for time discretisation

$$[C + \theta \Delta t K] T^{n+1} = (C - (1 - \theta) \Delta t K) T^n + \Delta t F^n \quad (12)$$

where θ is a parameter to define the art of the scheme, chosen as 0.5 for a semi-implicit scheme, and Δt is the time step.

The initial temperature of mould and epoxy are set to identical values, assuming that the resin is heating up quick during casting of plates. The heat transfer between the mould and oven via convection was considered to be small and therefore neglected. The temperature and degree of cure are update at each position over the thickness after every time step to account for the exothermic reaction during cure. The values for the density, thermal conductivity, k , and specific heat capacity, C_p , of the materials are summarised in Table 2. After a convergence analysis, 10 nodes per mm were used in the finite element analysis, where the time step was varied depending on the cure time, to produce approximately 3000 data points.

		Alum inium	Unmod ified	10N	20N
Density of formulation	[kg m ⁻³]	2700	1194	1247	1301
Density of epoxy in formulation	[kg m ⁻³]		1194	1185	1176
Thermal conductivity, k	[W m ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹]	135	0.2	0.23 [18]	0.26 [18]
Specific heat capacity, C_p	[J kg ⁻¹ °C ⁻¹]	1000	1700	1700	1700

Table 2: Values used for heat transfer modelling.

4 COMPARISON TO EXPERIMENTAL DATA

4.1 Resin temperature

The high exothermic reaction leads to a drastic temperature increase, which is not uniform over the thickness. An example of a 6 mm plate modelled with a mould temperature of 80 °C is shown in Figure 4 left. Until the maximum temperature is reached after about 60 seconds, the resin temperature increases drastically up to 170 °C while the mould temperature only increases about 10 °C. After the peak, the temperature decreases rapidly until equilibrium is reached. However, the significant temperature variation leads to non-uniform kinetic properties over the thickness, as will be discussed in the next sections.

A comparison between the measured and modelled temperature progression is shown in Figure 4 right for two cases, a 4-mm-thick plate cured at 80 °C, measured 0.8 mm from the edge, and a 3 mm plate cured at 100 °C, measured in the centre. The high temperature overshoot is replicated correctly in both cases. However, the measurement taken at 100 °C and measured in the middle of the plate shows some deviation after the peak. This is believed to be a result of the assumed constant thermal conductivity, which in reality will slightly increase with higher temperatures, resulting in faster heat transport.

Figure 4: (left) Resin and mould temperature during cure of a 6 mm plate with an initial temperature of 80 °C. (right) Comparison of experimental (points) and modelled temperature progression (lines).

The addition of silica nanoparticles can reduce the maximum temperature and temperature distribution over the thickness. The reduction is given by the decreased total heat of reaction in equation (7). Some examples are given in Table 3. It shall be noted that 200 °C is the decomposition temperature of the studied epoxy.

Material	Mould temperature (°C)	Thickness (mm)	Maximum temperature calculated (°C)	Thickness (mm)	Maximum temperature calculated (°C)
Unmodified	80	3	113	6	169
10N	80	3	105	6	160
20N	80	3	99	6	149
Unmodified	100	3	176	6	213
10N	100	3	166	6	201
20N	100	3	157	6	187

Table 3: Comparison of the maximum temperature for different curing scenarios and recipes.

4.1 Comparison of the glass transition temperature

The T_g was calculated using the DiBenedetto model (Equation (6)). The temperature variation over the thickness results in degree of cure and T_g variations over the thickness. An example is shown in Figure 5 left, where the T_g distribution over the thickness is compared for the unmodified epoxy, 10 wt% and 20 wt% silica nanoparticles for a 3 mm plate modelled with a mould temperature of 100 °C. The difference in the case of the unmodified epoxy is almost 11 °C, and this is reduced to 5.5 °C with the addition of 20 wt% silica nanoparticles. In order to compare the modelled T_g to the experimental data, the mean value over a thickness of 1 mm of the modelled data was taken, which roughly equals the thickness of the measured sample thickness during a DSC measurement. This results in a T_g of 106 °C on the edge for the unmodified 3 mm plate and 112 °C in the middle compared to 103 °C on the edge and 106 °C in the middle for 20 wt% silica nanoparticles. The temperature distribution over the thickness cannot be completely dismissed with the addition of silica nanoparticles, but is significantly reduced, leading to more uniform properties over the thickness. This becomes especially important for manufacturing of thick plates and / or when using fast-curing cycles.

A comparison for both the modelled and measured T_g values is shown in Figure 5 (right), where the agreement in general is excellent. A significant deviation can only be found for thick plates, e.g. 6 mm, measured in the middle. This again results from the assumed constant thermal conductivity, as was previously discussed. The values on the edge for those plates show excellent agreement between measured and modelled values.

Figure 5: (left) Variation of T_g over the thickness of a 3 mm plate and (right) comparison between measured and modelled T_g .

5 RHEOLOGICAL MODELLING

5.1 Measurements

It was shown above that the heat generation during cure can be reduced by the addition of silica nanoparticles. However, these particles increase the viscosity, which can increase the impregnation time for manufacturing of composites. The influence of the silica nanoparticles was studied using a plate-plate rheometer. The rapid viscosity increase allows no equilibration under isothermal conditions. Therefore the measurement was directly started and the time between the first contact of the resin with the preheated plate until the first measurement point was taken into account. Example results for 60 and 90 °C are shown in Figure 6, where the first data point was measured between 30 and 60 seconds. Dynamic measurement were performed from room temperature until full cure was reached with high heating rates of 10, 20 and 30 °C /min.

The addition of silica nanoparticles results in an increase of initial viscosity. This viscosity increase was believed to occur due to a reduction of polymer chain mobility (non-linear effect) and would be expected to result in an increased fibre impregnation time during composite processing. The effect was found to be relatively small for silica contents up to 20 wt% (Figure 6 left), whereas a higher wt% results in an exponential viscosity increase. It can be seen that already at a viscosity of 10 Pas, the influence of silica nanoparticles is negligible as the cure reaction kinetics dominated the evolution of the viscosity. The same goes for gelation which is measured when the ratio of loss modulus to storage modulus, δ has reached 45°. A comparison is shown in Figure 6 right for 70 °C and 100 °C.

Figure 6: (left) Shows the initial viscosity increase and (right) the nearly constant delta, δ (ratio of loss to storage modulus) with addition of silica nanoparticles.

5.2 Rheological modelling

For modelling of the rheological behaviour, a model based on the approach by Kiuna et al. [3] was used, where the viscosity, η , is modelled as a function of time and temperature in the explicit form

$$\eta(t, T) = \exp\left(\frac{\sum_i^n A_2 \exp\left(\frac{E_2}{RT}\right) t_i (A_4 \cdot T + E_4)}{E_3 \frac{1}{A_3 \exp\left(\sum_i^n A_2 \exp\left(\frac{E_2}{RT}\right) \frac{t_i}{E_3}\right)}}\right) A_1 \exp\left(\frac{E_1}{RT}\right) \quad (13)$$

The eight parameters for the rheological model, including four particle dependent parameters, are given in Table 4. The model can be used for all amounts of silica nanoparticles up to the maximum of 35.8 wt% (highest achievable amount with the addition of curing agent). The values for the parameters A_1 and E_1 , which represent the initial viscosity, as well as A_4 and E_4 to take into account the time shift, can be interpolated by third order polynomials shown in Table 4.

Parameter	Unmodified epoxy	10 N	20 N	35.8 N
A ₁	1.32 x 10 ⁻⁹	6.81 x 10 ⁻¹⁰	3.62 x 10 ⁻¹⁰	1.37 x 10 ⁻¹⁰
E ₁	52931	56049	58094	64000
A ₂	7518	7518	7518	7518
E ₂	-38710	-38710	-38710	-38710
A ₃	2.7	2.7	2.7	2.7
E ₃	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.2
A ₄	0.003	0.0046	0.006	0.007
E ₄	-0.409	-1.047	-1.519	-1.732

$$A_1 = -2.5684 \cdot 10^{-14} \cdot N^3 + 2.3459 \cdot 10^{-12} \cdot N^2 - 8.4316 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot N + 1.3156 \cdot 10^{-9}$$

$$E_1 = 0.36941 \cdot N^3 - 16.444 \cdot N^2 - 439.28 \cdot N + 52931$$

$$A_4 = -5.5238 \cdot 10^{-8} \cdot N^3 + 6.5714 \cdot 10^{-7} \cdot N^2 - 1.5895 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot N + 3.00 \cdot 10^{-3}$$

$$E_4 = 1.40495 \cdot 10^{-5} \cdot N^3 + 4.06514 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot N^2 - 6.92301 \cdot 10^{-2} \cdot N - 0.409$$

Table 4: Parameters used for the rheological model, where below are nanoparticle dependant equations to modify parameters (N is the wt% of silica).

The resulting model fit is shown in Figure 7 for the unmodified epoxy under isothermal conditions. The model fits the experimental data well during the initial stage of curing process up to 10 Pas. Higher viscosities were disregarded as the viscosity progression after 10 Pas is rapid, for example. at 100 °C, the viscosity is increased to 100 Pas after only 11 seconds, and after another 10 seconds gelation is reached. The calculated mean R² values of 0.978, 0.9774 and 0.965 describe the quality of fit for the unmodified, 10 wt% and 20 wt% silica nanoparticle-modified epoxies respectively and thus the models represent the experimental data well.

Figure 7: Rheological model (lines) compared to experimental measurements (points) for the unmodified epoxy and (inset) low viscosity range.

6. DISCUSSION

The thermal properties of a silica nanoparticle-modified fast-curing epoxy have been measured, and a kinetic and rheological model was successfully developed. In order to take the significant exothermic reaction during cure into account, the kinetic model was combined with the heat transfer equation. Hence, the degree of cure and resulting T_g may be predicted, including variation over the thickness. Comparison of the calculated T_g values with experimental data shows good agreement, and demonstrates the accuracy of the kinetic models.

No influence on the curing reaction itself was found with the addition of silica nanoparticles, but the particles reduce the total heat of reaction, and hence reduces the exothermic reaction during cure. This makes the manufacturing of thick parts and the use of fast cure cycles more controllable and leads to more uniform properties over the thickness. The influence of the silica nanoparticles on the initial viscosity was found to be small with up to 20 wt% of silica.

7. CONCLUSION

The addition of silica nanoparticles is a suitable method of reducing the exothermic heat generation during cure without influencing the curing reaction itself. This allows the use of fast cure cycles, makes the process more controllable and leads to more uniform properties over the thickness. Further the shrinkage can be reduced as was reported in [7]. Since the viscosity is only slightly increased with contents up to 20 wt%, the silica nanoparticles are well suited for liquid composite moulding (LCM) processes. The presented models may be used to predict the kinetic and rheological properties of manufactured and can be further integrated into flow models for optimised part filling and reduced void content of high-performance composite parts manufactured within minutes.

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